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Valuation of the intellectual capital of the enterprise: rent approach and its economic efficiency

KEYWORDS

intellectual capital;
rent approach;
intellectual capital valuation;
valuation methods

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The study of the rent approach to the assessment of intellectual capital is relevant and significant for understanding modern economic processes and improving business efficiency.

The article aims to develop methods for assessing an economic entity's intellectual capital using the rent approach.

Materials and methods. The author's toolkit for calculating rent income is proposed to consider the place of the rent approach in intellectual capital assessment. The calculations are based on economic and mathematical apparatus.

Research results. The authors propose evaluating the enterprise's intellectual capital using their method to determine the rental income it creates for a specific period. They present the dynamics of the main indicators for calculating the level of intellectualization of the enterprise (assessment of intellectual capital of the enterprise) by the rent approach. The analyzed enterprise periodically increased expenditures on its intellectual development, which led to an increase in the level of intellectualization of the enterprise and allowed formation of significant intellectual rent.

Conclusion. Evaluating intellectual capital over a specific period through identification of rental income is a new but promising area of research, which opens up several potential opportunities for forming intellectual capital management mechanisms at different management levels.

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Dmitriev, N. D. (2022). Valuation of the intellectual capital of the enterprise: rent approach and its economic efficiency. *Economic consultant*, (2), 4–12. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2022.2.1>

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world where information and knowledge are becoming key resources, intellectual capital (hereinafter IC) plays a significant role in creating competitive advantages. Companies with high levels of IC can adapt to market changes and innovate faster. Traditional asset valuation methods often fail to consider intangible components such as knowledge, employee skills, brands, and reputation. A rent-based approach offers a new way of looking at IR valuation, allowing a more accurate reflection of its contribution to economic performance. In addition, understanding how intellectual capital affects economic efficiency is becoming critical for modern businesses. Such knowledge enables companies to optimize resources, improve management, and increase profitability.

Thus, studying the rent approach to intellectual capital valuation is relevant and significant for understanding modern economic processes and improving business efficiency.

Literature review

The totality of the available scientific research allows the author to form an opinion of the importance of the enterprise's intellectual capital and the possibility of its qualitative assessment.

To conduct the study, we analyzed fundamental 20th-century works in human capital. T. Schultz [1] and F. Makhlop [2] considered the problems of investment in human capital and the education system. The relationship between investments in human capital and creation of competitive advantages of economic relations subjects at different levels of management was revealed. P. Drucker [3] analyzed how information society is formed and how importance of intangible elements in economic systems increases. T. Stewart is the classic of the intellectual capital theory; in his work [4], the author considered the elements that make up intellectual capital, namely attitudinal, human, and organizational.

Moreover, within the framework of the author's research, the works of practitioners in intellectual capital aroused interest. L. Edvinsson [5] noted that at the end of the last century, the efficiency of large international corporations was achieved mainly through the use of intellectual capital in economic activity. K. Sveiby [6] noted that intellectual capital is practically impossible to assess thoroughly since not all its elements are manageable and quantitative or qualitative calculations, i.e., people's intellectual activity is not regulated. At the same time, the assessment of the intellectual capital of the enterprise in monetary terms meets the interests of stakeholders, as well as the goals and objectives of strategic business development [7].

Modern globalization increases the importance of intellectual components in economic relations, and intellectual capital becomes the central element of economic and social

development. At the same time, several difficulties exist in determining economic efficiency which is associated with impossibility of quantitative calculations and lack of information to identify qualitative dependencies between different elements and processes of intellectualization [8].

The scientific community identifies various constituent elements of intellectual capital, which also gives rise to several problems in the assessment, as it is impossible to attribute a particular intangible asset to a specific aspect of intellectual capital [9]. Identifying the impact of each intellectual capital component on the enterprise's final performance is practically impossible, which leads to the search for more comprehensive methods. For this purpose, the research proposes to develop the existing methods of intellectual capital assessment and compare them with the classical ones.

Digital transformation and increasing the level of innovativeness pose challenges to modern society where people with specific skills, competencies, abilities, knowledge (including digital), and sufficient information play a fundamental role in economic processes [10; 11]. E. Zhilenkova et al. point out that reproduction of intellectual capital becomes one of the main tasks in forming the development strategy of economic entities, especially in industry [12].

In the practice of technologically developed countries, the share of material production is decreasing and giving way to the intellectual sphere, which gave impetus to the formation of personnel with a high level of competencies and relevant qualifications. As N. N. Trofimova rightly points out, ensuring the intellectualization of the economy and increasing its knowledge capacity is necessary to sustain all its elements [13]. Despite the importance of the knowledge economy and its principal element – intellectual capital, problems arise in conducting a fair assessment of the intellectual potential of economic entities (including intellectual enterprises [14]).

Comparing enterprises' final results with the dynamics of their intellectual capital and the level of intellectualization of the industry and the region [15] allows us to draw objective conclusions about effectiveness of economic activity and importance of the intellectual component of business in achieving the strategic success of the enterprise [16].

The above determines the relevance of research in intellectual capital and expansion of existing generally recognized approaches and concepts. In our opinion, the issues of assessing the enterprise's intellectual capital in conditions of constant development of economic theory and improvement of individual knowledge are not sufficiently elaborated. Since it is necessary to ensure its fair assessment for intellectual capital management, it is proposed to improve the existing approaches, focusing on the rent category.

Thus, the article aims to develop methods of assessing an economic entity's intellectual capital using the rent approach and compare the proposed approach with classical assessment

methods. For comparative analysis, we selected J. Tobin's cost approach, market capitalization, and added value approach and A. Pulik's method of added value approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Economic science offers a considerable number of methods for conducting intellectual capital valuation. Such methods include determining the amount of personnel and/or intellectual property costs, evaluating additional and alternative profits, identifying intellectual and economic potential, etc. [17]. Weak elaboration of the number of market criteria and complexity of displaying individual intellectual resources in reporting gives most methods an imperfect character. At the same time, there is an opportunity to obtain quantitative and qualitative estimates for further analysis and construction of dependency models. Classical methods for assessing the intellectual capital of the enterprise are the cost approach based on the Tobin coefficient, the method of market capitalization, and the added value of intellectual capital (Pulik) (VAIC).

To consider the place of the rent approach in methods of intellectual capital valuation, it is proposed to use the author's toolkit for calculating rent income and compare it with investments in the enterprise's intellectual development. The calculations are based on the economic and mathematical apparatus. The level of intellectualization is calculated by formula 1.

$$IC_{(rent)} = IR_{ie} / I_{ic} \quad (1)$$

$IC_{(rent)}$ is level of intellectualization of the enterprise;

IR_{ie} is value of intellectual rent;

I_{ic} is investment in intellectual development.

If investments in intellectual development are available, and their calculation does not create difficulties, the author's algorithm is proposed for use in calculating intellectual rent. To determine the investment in intellectual development, it is necessary to calculate the amount of investment that the enterprise directs to various intellectual development programs (for example, the cost of human capital development, personnel training, advanced training of human resources, innovative renewal, R&D, etc.). When calculating intellectual rent, the complexity lies in the calculation of normative values: the normative profitability coefficient in the industry can be taken as the average industry value of return on assets at the level of the region or country; the normative profit of the enterprise is calculated on the basis of the normative profitability and correction factors that take into account the difference of economic

entities due to the industry and territorial peculiarities of functioning. Intellectual rent is calculated according to formulas 2 and 3.

$$IR_{ie} = I - C - N_{pie}, \quad (2)$$

I is income of the enterprise;

C are expenses of the enterprise;

N_{pie} – normative profit for the year.

$$N_{pie} = A * ROA_{ia} * \beta_1 * \beta_2, \quad (3)$$

A is volume of assets of the enterprise at the end of the year;

ROA_{ia} is normative coefficient of return on assets in the industry;

β_1 is correction factor due to non-market factors;

β_2 is correction factor due to territorial differentiation.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Next, the enterprise's intellectual capital is evaluated by the author's method to determine the rental income it creates for a specific period. In the future, the obtained data will allow identifying the vulnerable sides of the enterprise's strategic development, for example, by means of multifactor analysis. As a result, it will be possible to develop recommendations to overcome them. Obtaining negative values of intellectual rent at the enterprise indicates the absence of intellectual capital due to the inefficiency of activity.

Table 1 presents the dynamics of the main indicators for calculating the values of the enterprise's intellectual rent. Table 2 shows the dynamics of the main indicators for calculating the level of intellectualization of the enterprise (assessment of intellectual capital of the enterprise) by the rent approach (author's method).

Table 1

Dynamics of the main indicators for calculating the values of intellectual rent of the enterprise (author's method)

Indicator/year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Total income	352.94	345.89	334.13	339.81	348.64
Costs	311.06	297.06	286.07	283.78	275.55
ROA_{ia}	4.56	4.55	4.65	4.62	4.39
A	4.81	4.73	4.86	5.07	5.2

β_1	1.15	1.19	1.17	1.2	1.19
β_2	1.23	1.26	1.23	1.26	1.29
N_{pie}	0.31	0.32	0.33	0.36	0.35
IR_{te}	41.57	48.5	47.73	55.67	72.74
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
337.48	338.5	352.04	337.25	338.26	340.63
281.89	290.63	304	309.77	304.2	291.42
4.41	4.59	4.44	4.48	4.29	4.47
5.13	4.9	4.95	5.14	4.97	5.03
1.16	1.12	1.18	1.16	1.1	1.1
1.31	1.36	1.33	1.31	1.33	1.33
0.34	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.31	0.33
55.25	47.53	47.69	27.13	33.76	48.88

Table 2

Dynamics of the leading indicators for calculating the intellectual capital of the enterprise by the rent approach (author's method)

Indicator/year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
I_{ic}	79.01	80.75	81.88	78.61	75.62
$IC_{(rent)}$	0.53	0.60	0.58	0.71	0.96
Δ (%)	-17.96%	14.15%	-2.95%	21.49%	35.83%
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
73.50	73.87	77.56	75.47	72.30	73.10
0.75	0.64	0.61	0.36	0.47	0.67
-21.85%	-14.41%	-4.43%	-41.54%	29.88%	43.23%

The analyzed enterprise periodically increased expenditures on its intellectual development, which led to an increase in the enterprise's intellectualization level and allowed it to form a significant intellectual rent. This fact testifies to increased efficiency due to competent investment policy and decreased return due to reduced investments. The result was to carry out the enterprise's intellectualization level using the author's approach.

A comparison of the rent approach and VAIC showed that the dynamics of indicators generally coincide. This result allows us to use the proposed approach to analyze intellectual capital.

Approbation of the proposed method at the enterprise shows the viability of the renting approach, on the basis of which it is acceptable to make a conclusion about the availability of intellectual resources at a particular point in time, to study the dynamics of changes based on the formation of intellectual rent, to build a comparative characterization of the obtained results with the data of other enterprises, taking into account the industry and territorial specifics.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Economic development and scientific and technological progress caused allocation of intellectual capital as a specific factor of production (information). At the same time, problems arise in conducting its fair assessment. Numerous studies confirm the significance of intellectual capital for innovative development and maintaining the strategic sustainability of economic entities. Intellectualization leads to formation of competitive advantages through technological transformation, reduction of production, transaction, and other types of costs. Empirical and applied works also confirm the effectiveness of intellectual development and its priority over traditional development.

The expansion of existing methods of intellectual capital assessment allows us to take a new look at this economic category. The feasibility of the study is confirmed by the possibility of using the approach proposed in the article to assess the intellectual capital of the enterprise, and in the future it is planned to determine its sufficiency and impact on the final results of the activity taking into account the normative indicators. The approbation allows us to conclude the significance of the approach and the possibility of its comparative analysis with other methods. Adapting the renting approach will allow revealing the significance of the intellectual component in creating excessive results for the enterprise.

The rent approach allows us to calculate the excess of profit over the average value on the market due to use of intellectual resources, which is especially significant in the conditions of widespread innovation development. The use of rent in assessing intellectual capital will allow identifying the dependence between the intellectual excess profit of an economic entity and investments in its intellectual development. Assessment of intellectual capital on a specific time through identification of rent income is a new but promising area of research which opens up a number of opportunities for forming intellectual capital management mechanisms at different levels of management.

The study of the rent approach to evaluation of intellectual capital is a scientific task that requires further comprehensive analysis and new methodological and applied approaches to enhance the understanding and effective management of intangible assets.

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Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2022/03/01/dmitriev/>

Received: Dec 30, 2021 | **Accepted:** Feb 10, 2022 | **Published:** Mar 1, 2022

Editor: Eduard A. Sosniv, National Research Tomsk State University, RUSSIA

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Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.